

Farming for the environment and climate: Why farmers in the German-French border region adopt agri-environmental practices

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Abstract

Empirical evidence on why farmers adopt agri-environmental practices remains fragmented, particularly regarding behavioral responses to incentives under the European Union's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). We adapt the COM-B behavioral model into a four-dimensional framework, **C**apability, **O**pportunity, **M**otivation, and systemic **C**ontext, and apply it to 62 semi-structured interviews with farmers living along the German-French border and receiving CAP support under divergent 2023-2027 national strategic plans. We show that barriers to adoption substantially outweigh promoting factors (71% vs. 28%), driven mainly by Opportunity factors (administrative complexity, contract rigidity, monitoring requirements) and Context factors (retail-sector power, trade exposure, limited societal recognition). Motivation is the only dimension where promoting factors dominate: intrinsic values and stewardship outweigh economic considerations on both sides of the border. We argue that agri-environmental support functions for most respondents as recognition and stabilization of practices already embedded in farm management rather than as catalysts of new behavior, yielding low additionality but high permanence. The cross-border comparison clarifies that what differs between France and Germany is less farmer motivation: the French approach bundles support into a single farm-wide commitment, while the German individual-measure approach reaches a broader population but leaves advisory support optional rather than embedded in the scheme. Scaling agri-environmental practice will depend less on paying *more* than on paying *better*: distinguishing measures that genuinely induce behavior change from those that recognize existing practice, preserving intrinsic motivation through simpler rules and more continuous advisory support, and aligning policy with the trade, market and societal conditions on which green farming livelihoods depend.

Keywords: farmer decision-making, agri-environmental scheme, agri-environment-climate measure, agri-environmental measure, eco-scheme, payments for ecosystem services, COM-C

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1 INTRODUCTION

Farmers in the European Union (EU) face increasing environmental, socio-political, and economic pressures. Against the increasingly felt consequences of climate change driven partly by agriculture itself (IPBES, 2019; IPCC, 2022; Wilting et al., 2017), society's expectations of farmers are changing. In addition to producing affordable, high-quality foods, farmers are increasingly expected to pay greater attention to environmental and climate concerns. Agriculture is expected to contribute to the EU's climate neutrality goal by 2050 and do so by reducing emissions at the member state level as part of the cross-sectoral sub-targets of the Effort Sharing Regulation, and by sequestering carbon under the Land Use, Land Use Change, and Forestry Regulation (LULUCF). The European Green Deal further provides for increased protection of biodiversity, reduced use of pesticides, and improved soil health, to be achieved through a significant expansion of organic farming, a "Farm to Fork" strategy, and measures under the Biodiversity Strategy (EC, 2019). However, this reorientation of EU environmental policy is taking place against a backdrop of structural pressures on the rural economy, where particularly small farmers are struggling to survive in the face of ongoing market consolidation, volatile commodity prices, and increasing production costs (Matthews, 2024).

The EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is the most important instrument for securing farmers' income, promoting environmentally sustainable agriculture, and strengthening the resilience of rural areas. A key element of this policy is the provision of financial incentives in exchange for agri-environmental practices. Some of these practices that EU member states can define apply to individual parcels, for example agroforestry, catch crops, buffer strips along watercourses, hedgerow maintenance, and grassland conservation. Others cover the whole farm, most notably organic farming. Further measures target animal welfare, for example a summer grazing premium for cattle or animal-friendly housing for pigs and poultry.

The CAP 2023-2027 channels incentives for these practices through two main instruments: (1) eco-schemes, which are annual, nationally designed area-based payments under CAP's Pillar I and serve as the central support instrument, and (2) Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AECMs), which involve multi-year commitments under Pillar II, are regionally adapted.¹ Together, these two instruments account for approximately 25% of the CAP's €307.4 billion total budget (European Commission, 2023).² The expected environmental benefits these practices generate (biodiversity, water and soil quality, climate regulation) have the character of public goods and positive externalities that markets do not reward, leaving farmers little private incentive to supply them beyond the

¹ Throughout this paper, we use 'agri-environmental scheme' (AES) as an umbrella term for the policy instruments themselves, covering eco-schemes, AECMs, and, more broadly, action-based payments for agri-environmental farming systems and practices (AES-supported practices). The on-farm activities these instruments support, encompassing both whole-farm systems (such as organic certification) and individual practices (such as extensive grassland management), together with equivalent activities that farmers carry out independently of any scheme, are referred to throughout as 'agri-environmental practices', or just 'practices'. Under the no-double-funding principle, the same action on the same land cannot receive both eco-scheme and AECM payment (Regulation (EU) 2021/2116, Article 36).

² Eco-schemes (Art. 31, Pillar I) account for about 15% of total CAP public expenditure (44.71 billion €), and agri-environment-climate commitments (AECMs, Art. 70, Pillar II) for about 11% (33.21 billion €). Together they represent about a quarter of the 307.4 billion € budget of the CAP 2023-2027, which includes 43.3 billion € of national co-financing (European Commission, 2023). These numbers include organic farming. The remaining three quarters fund mainly direct income support under Pillar I. The so called "Basic Income Support for Sustainability" is the largest single instrument, at about 31% of total CAP public expenditure (96.7 billion €). The rest covers redistributive and young-farmer income support, coupled income support, sectoral interventions, and Pillar II measures other than AECMs, such as investments and support for areas facing natural constraints.

regulatory baseline. Correcting this market failure through public payment is the long-standing economic rationale for such instruments (Pigou, 1920; Engel et al., 2008).

We thus suggest that eco-schemes and AECMs function as a form of Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES) (Wunder, 2005, 2015; Kaiser et al., 2021), compensating farmers for additional costs and income foregone when adopting practices that deliver environmental benefits beyond the regulatory baselines defined by Statutory Management Requirements (SMRs) and Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs). This regulatory threshold defined in Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 determines what qualifies for payment, but it does not ensure that the payment changes behavior. For the payment to make a real and lasting difference, the supported practices should also be *additional* to business-as-usual³ and remain in place *permanently* after the payment ends. These two conditions are part of a broader, multidimensional notion of effectiveness, which also requires realizing the expected benefits at a *cost-effective* level, within the desired *time* frame, and at scale, both within a single *participating* farm (scaling up) and across many farms (scaling out) (Mayr et al., 2025). The Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 defines common principles and eligibility criteria for eco-schemes and AECMs, while Member States specify the actual interventions in their national CAP Strategic Plans.

In this article, we investigate the reasons why farmers adopt or reject these instruments, which we believe are poorly understood. Although recent reviews have expanded the analytical focus of sustainable farming practice adoption beyond purely economic models to include behavioral factors such as dispositional traits, social norms and cognitive biases (Canessa et al., 2024; Dessart et al., 2019), the existing literature remains largely focused on scheme-level determinants of adoption (payment levels, administrative procedures, and contract design) without sufficiently accounting for broader framework conditions such as market dynamics, international competition, and societal appreciation of environmental public goods. Such knowledge gap needs to be addressed as barriers at the program level require a revision of CAP instruments, whereas structural barriers necessitate measures that extend beyond agri-environmental policy. Furthermore, existing research is predominantly based on single-country studies (Bartkowski et al., 2023), offering limited insight into how divergent EU's CAP architectures shape farmers' adoption behavior across different institutional, agro-ecological, and market contexts, including cross-border settings where farmers operate under distinct governance frameworks but face similar environmental conditions. A better understanding of the factors that enable or hinder farmers' engagement with agri-environmental policy instruments across such contexts is therefore crucial for designing more effective and transferable policy approaches.

To fill this gap, we examine the adoption of agri-environmental practices and participation in agri-environmental schemes (AES), in particular under CAP, by German and French farmers in the Upper Rhine region, a cross-border area with similar biophysical conditions but differing socio-political and administrative contexts. Specifically, we seek to (1) document the extent of agri-environmental practice and participation in AES; (2) assess the additionality and permanence of the AES-supported practice uptake; and (3) identify the factors influencing the adoption of agri-environmental practices. In doing so, we shed light on three related dimensions of PES "effectiveness": participation, additionality and permanence. The cross-border analytical focus exploits the contrasting policy and institutional frameworks in France and Germany as a natural experiment, allowing observed differences in adoption patterns and farmer perceptions to be attributed to divergent policy

³ EU's baseline definition is a regulatory threshold, not a behavioral test. Two further senses of additionality should be distinguished from it. Financial (or behavioral) additionality asks whether the payment was necessary for the practice to be adopted. Ecological (or environmental) additionality asks whether the practice delivers environmental benefits beyond what would have occurred anyway. Going beyond the regulatory baseline ensures neither. The evaluative focus of this study is financial additionality.

architectures rather than to biophysical or market confounders. We adapt the COM-B behavioral model (Michie et al., 2011) into a four-dimensional framework capturing farmers' **C**apability, **M**otivation, the **O**pportunities afforded by policy design, and the broader systemic **C**ontext. This extension allows us to distinguish AES-level opportunities from contextual factors, clarifying which barriers necessitate CAP redesign versus broader structural reform.

2 UNDERSTANDING THE ADOPTION OF AGRI-ENVIRONMENTAL PRACTICES

Research on farmer adoption of agri-environmental practices spans several theoretical traditions, each illuminating a different facet of the decision to implement (or refrain from implementing) practices that benefit the environment. Because we analyze both AES-supported practices and non-AES-supported practices that farmers carry out independently, we draw selectively on three complementary theories. The Theory of Planned Behavior captures the socio-psychological drivers of adoption, and Random Utility Theory the economic trade-offs behind participation. Self-Determination Theory is complementary rather than a special case of the other two. It specifies the quality of motivation that they leave unspecified, which shapes both whether a supported practice is additional and whether it is permanent once payments end. We chose these three because together they span the psychological, economic, and motivational dimensions of voluntary behavioral change and AES participation. Other adoption theories tend to emphasize only one of these dimensions, so no single framework would have covered all three.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) frames adoption as the outcome of three proximal antecedents: attitudes towards the practice, perceived social pressure (subjective norms), and perceived behavioral control over its implementation. Applied to the uptake of (AES-supported) practices, recent evidence shows that attitudes, intentions and related socio-psychological constructs are among the most consistent predictors of farmers' adoption of sustainable practices, alongside subjective norms and perceived behavioral control (Swart et al., 2023; Dessart et al., 2019; Schaub et al., 2023). Systematic reviews caution, however, that the quality of Theory of Planned Behavior operationalization varies considerably across studies, and that the framework risks underspecifying the structural and contextual conditions under which these constructs operate (Sok et al., 2021). Burton (2004) offers a foundational critique of naively individualistic behavioral approaches in agricultural studies.

Random Utility Theory (Lancaster, 1966; McFadden, 1974), typically operationalized through discrete choice experiments, treats farmers instead as utility-maximizers who weigh expected payments against opportunity costs, transaction costs, risk and contractual constraints. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses of this literature consistently show that monetary compensation matters but is rarely the sole driver of stated participation: contract flexibility, duration, monitoring requirements and administrative burden emerge as equally decisive design attributes (Tyllianakis & Martin-Ortega, 2021; Lastra-Bravo et al., 2015; Mamine et al., 2020; Schulze et al., 2023).

The Theory of Planned Behavior and Random Utility Theory both treat motivation as a quantity to be increased rather than as a state that differs in kind. To capture this quality of motivation, we therefore draw on Self-Determination Theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000), which differentiates motivation by quality rather than quantity. Self-Determination Theory distinguishes a continuum of motivational states from *amotivation* (no intention to act), through *external regulation* (action contingent on rewards or sanctions) and *introjected regulation* (action driven by internalized pressure such as guilt or social approval), to *identified regulation* (the behavior is consciously valued as personally important) and, at the most autonomous end, *intrinsic motivation* (engagement undertaken for its own sake). The first two types are commonly grouped as controlled motivations, the latter two as autonomous motivations. Self-Determination Theory further posits three basic psychological needs whose

satisfaction underpins motivation quality: *autonomy* (experiencing one’s actions as self-endorsed), *competence* (feeling effective in carrying them out), and *relatedness* (feeling socially connected through them). The two components are linked: need satisfaction fosters the internalization of behaviors along the continuum toward autonomous motivation, while need frustration impedes this process and sustains controlled regulation or amotivation. Empirical applications to farming show that autonomously motivated farmers adopt practices more intensively and internalize program goals, while externally regulated participation stays contingent on continued support (Jambo et al., 2019; Zhu & Chen, 2024; Winkler-Schor et al., 2025). This carries a design concern, because financial rewards and strict controls can crowd out the intrinsic motivation behind lasting commitment, though the evidence on crowding is mixed (Akers & Yasué, 2019; Chervier et al., 2019).

Beyond these theoretical lenses, a large empirical literature has synthesized the determinants of adoption across studies and contexts. Table 1 summarizes eight major reviews of agri-environmental practice adoption. Common themes recur such as payment adequacy, advisory support, social norms, contract design but the reviews differ markedly in scope, method, and conceptual framing of adoption factors. These range from the economic, structural, social, and policy-design perspective of Lastra-Bravo et al. (2015) and psychological taxonomies (Dessart et al., 2019) to multilevel hierarchies (Klebl et al., 2024), and from quantitative meta-analytic frameworks (Canessa et al., 2024; Schaub et al., 2023) to governance-architecture lenses (Podruzsik & Fertó, 2024). Recent systematic reviews also caution that several frequently invoked determinants are less consistent across contexts than is sometimes assumed (Schaub et al., 2023; Thompson et al., 2024), with Mozzato et al. (2018) showing systematically that geographical context and adopter cohorts explain a substantial share of these inconsistencies.

Table 1: Major reviews of agri-environmental practice adoption - methodological type, conceptual framing, and key findings

Review	Methodological type and scope	Conceptual framing of factors	Key findings
Lastra-Bravo et al. (2015)	Qualitative meta-analysis of EU AES adoption studies	Economic, structural, social and policy-design drivers	Fair payment levels, lower household dependence on farm income, farmer age and education, presence of a successor, and the possibility of progressive rather than step-based changes are found as key drivers of adoption. Beyond AES design itself, complementary rural and household-level policies are identified as decisive for participation.
Dessart et al. (2019)	Policy-oriented narrative review	Three-level behavioral taxonomy: <i>dispositional, social, cognitive</i>	Dispositional traits (openness, environmental concern, lifestyle objectives) and social factors (descriptive norms, opinion of social referents, status motives) are robustly associated with adoption. Cognitive factors (knowledge, perceived benefits, risk perception) drive the adoption of specific practices. The review recommends segmenting farmers by socio-demographic profile and combining mandatory and voluntary instruments.
Schaub et al. (2023)	Systematic review	Two-axis framework: <i>behavioral factors vs. opportunity costs</i>	Many relationships between determinants and AES participation are not as consistent as commonly portrayed and depend strongly on context. Robustly positive: agricultural training and advice, peer relationships, positive AES attitudes. Robustly relevant: market conditions, profitability, contract flexibility. Several factors often assumed to drive adoption (environmental attitude, trust, farm size) are context-dependent or insignificant in most of the cases included in the review.
Canessa et al. (2024)	Systematic review of quantitative AECM participation studies	Frequency and direction of significance across quantitative variables	Variables capturing information flows, interpersonal communication, and satisfaction with AECM design were positively and consistently linked to adoption, including in studies where they were tested less frequently.

Review	Methodological type and scope	Conceptual framing of factors	Key findings
Klebl et al. (2024)	Systematic review	Multilevel framework across five hierarchical scales: <i>society, landscape, community, farm, individual</i>	Engagement requirements and contract-design elements matter independently of alignment with existing practice and perceived opportunity. The review calls for co-design and semi-qualitative approaches in scheme development. Adoption decisions are complex and non-directional, shaped by interacting factors across levels and embedded in regional and cultural contexts. Intrinsic values, attitudes, and a sense of environmental responsibility can hold equal or greater weight than economic reasoning, suggesting that purely economic models systematically under-explain observed behavior.
Podruzsik & Fertó (2024)	Narrative literature review	Governance and incentive-architecture lens	Effective AES require adaptive-management strategies, incentive structures aligned with environmental objectives, and inclusive governance mechanisms. Context-specific design accounting for farm characteristics, socio-economic conditions and institutional arrangements is a recurring recommendation, alongside more rigorous cost–benefit analyses and standardized monitoring frameworks. Socio-demographic and farm-structural variables are frequently tested but more often insignificant than significant. Cognitive and proximal attitudinal variables show stronger effects than dispositional ones. Media influence, identity, advisors, and social norms are significant in 50–70% of models where tested, though they remain comparatively under-examined. Formal institutional factors are poorly represented in the literature, and existing evidence is inconclusive.
Thompson et al. (2024)	Systematic literature <i>map</i> (descriptive synthesis)	Personal / social / formal-institutional / structural taxonomy (ISM- and TPB-inspired)	Apparent contradictions in the literature on factor effects are largely explained when geographical and temporal context are considered: farm-structural factors show geographical patterns, while management and economic factors follow temporal trends across early and late adopters. The review provides systematic evidence that factor effects on adoption of Environmentally Friendly Farming Practices are not universal but context-dependent.
Mozzato et al. (2018)	Qualitative meta-analysis (worldwide)	TPB/Reasoned Action lens organized across <i>farm, farmer, informational, social factors</i> ; explicit moderation by <i>geographical region and temporal adopter cohorts</i>	

Source: Authors' own compilation.

Empirical evidence indicates that AECMs tend to attract farmers whose current practices already align closely with AES requirements (Bartkowski et al., 2023), a pattern with direct implications for the additional environmental gains these AES can deliver. Sub-regional uptake data are rarely published, which limits the granularity at which spatial heterogeneity can be analyzed. Evidence specifically on additionality and permanence remains comparatively thin and often points to limitations. Quasi-experimental evidence indicates that a significant share of CAP payments rewards practices that farmers would have implemented anyway (Chabé-Ferret & Subervie, 2013), a pattern corroborated by audit-based environmental effectiveness assessments at EU level (Alliance Environnement, 2019; European Court of Auditors, 2020).

Evidence on permanence is thinner and largely confined to single-scheme studies, which suggest that environmental gains can be reversed once contracts end if the underlying motivation was external (Calvet et al., 2019; Kuhfuss et al., 2016). Mayr et al. (2025) argue that additionality and permanence are not intrinsic properties of a measure but depend jointly on scheme design and on the configuration of farmer motivations and capabilities at adoption, a perspective that motivates the joint examination

of uptake and effectiveness in this paper. Robust evidence for the CAP 2023–2027 period is still emerging, particularly at the practice level and in cross-country comparisons.

Three gaps emerge from the theories and empirical reviews discussed above, and together they motivate the design and analytical-conceptual framing of the present study. First, comparative empirical research across institutional contexts remains rare in the agri-environmental adoption literature, despite its analytical potential to disentangle policy-design effects from biophysical and market conditions. Most studies looking at agri-environmental practice adoption focus on a single country or compare sub-national regions within one EU Member State, holding the policy framework largely constant. Cross-border designs, which can vary policy architecture while keeping agro-ecological and market conditions comparable, are notably scarce in the AES literature. Even broader multi-country adoption studies remain limited, with notable exceptions such as Bartkowski et al. (2023) and Arata & Sckokai (2016). Most do not exploit border configurations to isolate institutional effects. This is particularly limiting given ongoing debates about the appropriate balance between harmonization and subsidiarity in the CAP's decentralized governance (Regulation (EU) 2021/2115).

Second, although several studies suggest that CAP payments face additionality and permanence challenges, evidence for the 2023–2027 period remains scarce, especially at the level of individual practices and in comparison across Member States. Most existing assessments focus on selected AES in single countries, and few connect the additionality observed back to the configuration of farmer motivations and capabilities that the design of the AES either supports or undermines. Third, the theoretical and empirical diversity documented above has produced numerous overlapping categorizations of adoption factors but few analytical frameworks that explicitly distinguish between (a) what the farmer-farm-unit can do, (b) what internally drives the farmer to act, (c) which external opportunities are made available (typically by AES design and the local environment), and (d) which broader systemic conditions frame all of the above. An integrative lens that preserves this analytical separation while synthesizing the theoretical diversity of the field is currently missing from the CAP adoption literature.

Towards a synthesizing framework: COM-C

Precisely, to address the third gap, we draw on the COM-B model of behavior (Michie et al., 2011), which organizes the determinants of Behavior into three interacting components defined by their leverage points for intervention rather than by disciplinary tradition: **C**apability, **O**pportunity and **M**otivation. COM-B is well-suited as an integrating frame because it accommodates determinants identified through Theory of Planned Behavior, Random Utility Theory and Self-Determination Theory alike, while keeping analytically distinct what farmers can do, what they want to do and what their environment makes possible.

Two limitations of the original COM-B model become apparent when applied to farmer behavior in the CAP context. First, COM-B was developed for individual behavior and does not explicitly address the operational unity of “farmer-and-farm” in agricultural production. Second, its ‘opportunity’ component conflates AES- and local-level conditions with broader systemic factors (markets, trade, regulatory coherence, societal appreciation of agriculture) that operate at a different scale and require fundamentally different policy responses. Recent extensions, notably the Socio-Ecological COM-B of (Nguyen-Trung et al., 2025), have addressed the latter by embedding Opportunity in nested ecological layers.

In this paper we propose a contextualized extension that we term COM-C, in which a fourth analytical category (**C**ontext) captures structural conditions operating at systems level that shape adoption possibilities but require complementary intervention beyond agri-environmental policy. The full

operationalization of COM-C, including the extension of Capability to the farmer-farm-unit and the criteria distinguishing Capability from Opportunity, is set out in Section 3.3 as part of the methodological-analytical strategy as well as in the Supplementary Material.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

We employ a cross-border, most-similar-systems case study design in the German–French Upper Rhine region, combining qualitative interviews with farmers, quantitative structural farm data, and analysis of the regulatory frameworks on each side of the border. The two sides of the study area share similar agro-ecological conditions and market integration but differ in their institutional and administrative arrangements for implementing CAP measures, allowing observed differences in adoption patterns and farmer perceptions to be attributed to divergent policy architectures rather than to biophysical or structural confounders.

The research design is structured around the three objectives stated in section 1. For objectives 1 and 2, documenting the extent of agri-environmental practice and incentive uptake, and assessing the additionality and permanence of AES-supported practices, we collected quantitative data through structured interview questions and official CAP beneficiary databases, complemented by dedicated items on counterfactual adoption and post-contract continuation. For objective 3, identifying the factors influencing adoption, we conducted semi-structured interviews and applied a thematic coding strategy from which the COM-C framework was developed iteratively (see section 3.2), complemented by standardized motivational items derived from Self-Determination Theory. The following sections describe the study area and its contrasting institutional settings (detailed in Supplementary Material) and the data collection, processing and analysis procedures.

3.1 Study area: German-French Upper Rhine cross-border region

The study focuses on two sub-regional administrative units situated along the German–French Upper Rhine: The Arrondissement of Molsheim (France, Region of Grand Est, Alsace, Bas-Rhin, hereafter “Molsheim”) and the Landkreis Ortenau (Germany, Baden-Württemberg, hereinafter “Ortenau”) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The trinational Upper Rhine region with the Arrondissement of Molsheim (France) (blue) and Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) (orange)

Source: Adapted from GeoRhena 2021/CeA MapID: 01_2021_281

The broader Upper Rhine region covers approximately 18,000 km² and is home to more than 20,000 farms (Statistische Ämter am Oberrhein, 2024). The two units share a similar topography, with extensive agricultural and viticulture areas in the Rhine valley giving way to forested low mountain ranges, the Vosges in France, and the Black Forest in Germany, both of which contain open pastureland.

Despite their difference in administrative size, the study areas are strikingly similar in agricultural structure (Table 2). Both are characterized by small-scale farming, mixed arable-grassland systems, and significant topographic constraints due to mountainous terrain (MAASA, 2021; Observatoire des territoires & ANCT, 2023, 2024; Statistisches Landesamt Baden-Württemberg, 2021a, 2021b). What differs is the agri-environmental policy architecture through which farmers access support. German farmers in Ortenau enroll individually and directly in the Baden-Württemberg AECM programs like FAKT II. The lower agricultural authorities administer these applications and the associated controls, with their mandate set out in the Landwirtschafts- und Landeskulturgesetz (Land Baden-Württemberg, 1972). Since the 2015 reform of advisory funding, specific technical advice is delegated to accredited private organizations rather than provided by the authorities (Birke et al., 2022). In France, AECMs are territorialized and become available only where a project operator (*structure animatrice*), typically an agricultural chamber, a public authority, or a nature park, proposes and animates a local AECM project (see Supplementary Material).

Table 2: Key agricultural characteristics of the Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France)

Characteristic	Ortenau (DE)	Molsheim (FR)	Sources
Administrative area	1,860 km ²	771 km ²	ortenaukreis.de , insee.fr
Average farm size	18 ha	24 ha	Statistisches Landesamt BW (2021a), MAA (2021), Observatoire des territoires (2023)
Arable land (% UAA)	49%	42%	Statistisches Landesamt BW (2021b), MAA (2021), Observatoire des territoires (2023)
Permanent grassland (% UAA)	38%	33%	Statistisches Landesamt BW (2021b), MAA (2021), Observatoire des territoires (2023)
Mountain topography (% area)	49%	42%	Stat. Landesamt BW (2025), Observatoire des territoires (2024)

Notes : UAA= Utilized Agricultural Area ; BW=Baden-Württemberg; MAA=Ministère de l'Agriculture, de l'Agro-alimentaire et de la Souveraineté alimentaire;

Source: Authors' own development.

3.2 Data collection

Data were collected through 62 semi-structured interviews with farmers, 31 in Ortenau (Germany) and 31 in Molsheim (France), conducted by the first author between December 2024 and June 2025. Interviews were held primarily in person on the farms (n=42), with telephone or video alternatives offered for scheduling convenience (n=20), lasted between 30 and 75 minutes, and were conducted in participants' native languages (German or French). All interviews were audio-recorded with informed consent.

The semi-structured interview guide combined closed-ended questions on farm characteristics, AES participation, and practice implementation with open-ended questions on adoption decisions, perceived barriers and enablers. Four dedicated questions captured additionality and permanence at both farm and individual measure levels. Motivational orientations were assessed through 20 standardized Self-Determination Theory-based items rated on a 4-point Likert scale - the only element of the guide structured along a specific theoretical framework. Because Self-Determination Theory diagnoses motivation through actually performed behavior, the framework applies only to farmers who implement at least one of the assessed practices; in our sample, every respondent reported implementing at least one agri-environmental practice (Section 4.1), so the SDT analysis covers the full sample (N = 62).

The guide was pre-tested with three farmers near the Landkreis Ortenau in November 2024 and refined based on their feedback (see Supplementary Material for the full interview guide). Together with CAP beneficiary data, the closed-ended items provided the quantitative basis for documenting practice and incentive uptake (objective 1) and assessing additionality and permanence (objective 2), while the open-ended questions generated the qualitative material for identifying adoption factors (objective 3). The COM-C lens introduced earlier emerged through iterative coding of this qualitative material as the analytical organization that produced the clearest thematic separation across alternatives (see section 3.3 for the full operationalization), and the cross-border most-similar-systems design made it possible to trace how the same dimensions operated differently under French and German policy architectures.

Farmers were recruited by randomly contacting individuals drawn from official CAP beneficiary databases for 2022–2023, published by Germany and France (accessible via agriculture.ec.europa.eu). These databases list all CAP payment recipients, making it possible to identify both farmers participating in AES and those receiving only basic income support, thereby capturing perspectives from across the spectrum of agri-environmental engagement. Drawing from an official register rather

than relying on snowball or volunteer recruitment reduced the risk of systematically overrepresenting farmers already connected to advisory networks or professional organizations (Sadler et al., 2010).

Table 3 summarizes the structural and socio-demographic characteristics of the sample. The sample is evenly distributed across the two study regions. Grassland farming is the most common farm type, followed by arable and perennial farming (primarily viticulture). Nearly half of the respondents are part-time family farmers, and half operate in mountain areas. Farm sizes vary considerably, with a mean size of 41 hectares. On average, farmers have nearly 30 years of experience and most hold an agricultural qualification. The two study areas show distinct specialization profiles: French respondents lean more heavily toward perennial farming (viticulture), while German respondents are more strongly represented in arable and grassland farming.

Table 3: Characteristics of 62 farms interviewed in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France)

Variable	Category / Unit	%	Median	Mean (SD)	Range	n
<i>Farmer characteristics</i>						
Age	years	–	52.0	52.1 (14.2)	31-89	62
Gender	male	90%	–	–	–	62
Children	with children	85%	–	–	–	62
Education (agricultural)	with degree	74%	–	–	–	61
Highest general education	EQF level	–	5.0	4.9 (1.3)	2-8	62
Experience in agriculture	years	–	27.0	29.5 (13.1)	5-69	61
Successor identified	yes	63%	–	–	–	24
Member of agricultural organization	yes	79%	–	–	–	62
Part-time farmer	yes	45%	–	–	–	62
<i>Farm characteristics</i>						
Farm size	hectares	–	20.0	40.8 (49.6)	0.5-300	62
Farm type	arable/grassland/perennial/mixed/other	24/42/16/13/5%	–	–	–	62
Terrain	in mountains/flats	50/50%	–	–	–	62
Region	Germany/France	50/50%	–	–	–	62
<i>Information, social variables</i>						
Subsidy self-awareness	mean score	–	3.0	2.5 (0.8)	1-4	58
Neighbor adopter contact	yes	33%	–	–	–	40

Notes: Percentages are based on available responses (n). EQF = European Qualifications Framework (1 = Basic general knowledge; introductory education, 8 = Doctorate). Subsidy self-awareness measured on a 1–4 scale (1 = very low, 4 = very high). Medians, means and ranges are shown for continuous variables; standard deviations (SD) in parentheses for reference. The sample for “successor identified” is restricted to farmers aged ≥60.

Source: Authors' own development.

Data processing and analysis

Audio recordings were transcribed in their original languages (German and French). The subsequent iterative coding process was led by the first author. Statements were de-identified before processing. A large language model (Claude Opus 4, Anthropic), operated in a mode that does not retain inputs or use them for training, then assisted in mapping these statements to the COM-C framework. All AI-generated categorizations were treated as preliminary suggestions; the author manually reviewed, validated, and finalized the entire analytical framework, retaining full interpretive control. Through

multiple rounds of coding, codes and sub-codes were developed from the data, progressively refining and consolidating emerging themes. The final codebook organizes these codes into the four analytical dimensions of the COM-C framework (see Section 3.3), with sub-codes capturing specific barriers and enabling factors (see Table 7). This structure was chosen because, relative to alternative categorizations inspired by the literature, it produced the sharpest thematic separation and the least conceptual overlap while remaining embedded in a well-tested theoretical framework. Ultimately, the coding aimed to identify recurring themes and valences across the two study areas, alongside the relationship between adoption factors and AES participation. Finally, structural associations were quantified using Phi coefficients.

3.3 Conceptual-analytical framework

Given the theoretical diversity documented in section 2, we organized our findings into an analytical framework adapting the COM-B model (Michie et al., 2011) to our cases and extending it to incorporate systemic context. Building on the feasibility-desirability distinction in the context of PES (Mayr et al., 2025), differentiating between wanting to adopt practices (desirability) and being able to adopt them (feasibility), we recognize that feasibility operates across the internal resources of the farmer-farm-unit, the external opportunities provided by AES and the local environment, and broader systemic contexts. The same desirability and feasibility logic shapes not only whether farmers participate but whether their participation scales up rather than merely out.

This led us to propose a COM-C framework comprising four analytical categories:

- *Capability* addresses farm-level feasibility, that is, whether the farmer-farm-unit possesses the knowledge, skills, physical resources and remaining absorptive capacity needed to implement a practice. We extend the original COM-B notion of individual capability to the operational unit of farmer and farm, recognizing that adoption constraints frequently arise from the farm system (e.g. land availability, labor capacity, soil conditions) rather than from the farmer alone.
- *Motivation* captures all conscious and unconscious drivers of the farmer's willingness to act, encompassing economic calculations, operational considerations, environmental values, and identity. Following Self-Determination Theory, we further distinguish the quality of motivation along the autonomy continuum.
- *Opportunity* comprises factors outside the individual that make adoption possible or prompt it, operationalized at the AES and local level: payment adequacy, administrative burden, contract design, advisory support, monitoring arrangements and social environment.
- *Context* represents our extension from COM-B to COM-C. It captures structural conditions operating at the systems level (market dynamics, trade exposure, policy coherence, rural infrastructure and socio-cultural norms) that shape adoption possibilities but lie beyond the reach of AES design and require complementary intervention.

Categories are analytically distinct but empirically interconnected: a farmer may possess the capability and motivation to adopt a practice but faces opportunity barriers in AES design or contextual constraints in market conditions that prevent action. This separation clarifies intervention leverage: Capability and Motivation barriers call for training, advisory services and behavioral design; Opportunity barriers call for AES redesign; Context barriers require structural reform beyond agri-environmental policy. Table 7 presents the full cluster structure; for the detailed definition and full operationalization of each dimension, see Supplementary Material.

Figure 2: The COM-C framework: a contextualized extension of the COM-B behavioral model. At the core, the farmer-farm-unit's adoption decision is shaped by Motivation (desirability) and Capability (farm-level feasibility). This decision is embedded within Opportunity, the scheme- and local-level conditions comprising policy design, the social environment, and the biophysical feasibility of the practice itself. Opportunity is in turn embedded within Context, the broader systemic conditions of markets, trade, regulatory coherence, and societal appreciation that condition whether scheme-level opportunities translate into adoption. Practice adoption is distinguished as incentivized (with financial or technical support) or non-incentivized.

Source: Authors' own development.

3.4 Limitations

Several limitations should be kept in mind. The 31 interviews per study area do not allow statistically robust testing of differences across the two countries or across measure types. The coding of statements rests on subjective interpretation. We mitigated this through iterative coding rounds that revised both the codebook and the analytical framework against the empirical material. All findings rest on farmers' own reports, which were not independently verified and may be affected by social desirability. The cross-border contrast in particular cannot be attributed to policy design alone, since Ortenau and Molsheim also differ in farm structure, advisory networks, and market channels. Finally, the cross-sectional design observes motivations and practices at a single point in time. It captures the level of motivation, not its change over the course of scheme participation. Our reading of the absence of crowding out therefore rests on this level and on the recognition mechanism, not on observed change over time.

We nonetheless consider the results reported below robust, especially our central finding of low financial additionality. The 62 interviews give a coherent overall picture. The triangulation of qualitative coding, the standardized motivation survey, and the structural associations between farm and practice characteristics reinforces it. The results also align with quasi-experimental and audit evidence from elsewhere in Europe (Alliance Environnement, 2019; Chabé-Ferret & Subervie, 2013;

European Court of Auditors, 2020), and with an earlier regional administrative survey of AECM beneficiaries in the Grand Est (DRAAF Grand Est & Région Grand Est, 2020), despite differences in method, period, and scale.

4 RESULTS

The results are organized in three sections: first, an overview of the type and extent of agri-environmental practices adopted; second, an assessment of the additionality and permanence of incentivized practices; and third, an analysis of factors shaping adoption structured according to the COM-C framework.

4.1 Type and extent of agri-environmental practices

The 62 surveyed farms exhibit a broad yet heterogeneous range of agri-environmental practices (Table 4, see Supplementary Material for a cross-border breakdown). Whole-farm certification schemes, namely organic farming⁴ and High Environmental Value (*Haute Valeur Environnementale*, HVE)⁵, cover about one-third of holdings. Some French farms also enter the eco-scheme through the “practices pathway” (*voie des pratiques*), through which 10% of all holdings participate.⁶ Organic farming is particularly prevalent among perennial farms, where viticulturists represent the largest group of certified producers. Despite the availability of comprehensive certification frameworks, most farms implement non-certified parcel-based agri-environmental practices.

⁴ EU organic farming is regulated under Regulation (EU) 2018/848, which sets harmonized minimum standards across the EU, including restrictions on synthetic inputs, a ban on GMOs, and mandatory third-party certification. See <https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/organic-farming>

⁵ To reach the HVE level, a farm must meet stringent, comprehensive metrics across four themes defined in the “Plan de contrôle niveau 3”: biodiversity, phytosanitary (pesticide) strategy, fertilization, and water management. See <https://hve-asso.com/la-hve/> and <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/certification-environnementale-mode-demploi-pour-les-exploitations>

⁶ The “voie des pratiques” is one of the access routes to the French CAP eco-scheme (éco-régime), requiring farms to implement agro-ecological practices across their entire holding, such as crop diversification, limits on soil disturbance (e.g. reduced ploughing of permanent grasslands), and minimum vegetation cover in perennial crops. It constitutes a voluntary scheme with defined environmental performance thresholds and payment levels, and is one of three non-cumulative pathways (alongside certification and biodiversity features) to qualify for eco-scheme support. Unlike certification-based pathways (e.g. organic farming or HVE), it is not based on external labels but on the direct implementation of specified farming practices. See <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/telecharger/135090>

Table 4: Distribution of 186 agri-environmental farming systems and individual practices as claimed by 62 farms in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France) for 2024

Category	Type of agri-environmental system/practice	n	% of sample (N=62)	% of n AES-supported	Main farm type(s)			
					Perennial	Grass-land	Arable/Market	Mixed
AGRI-ENVIRONMENTAL FARMING SYSTEMS	Organic farming (certified)	10	16%	100%	•			
	Organic farming (uncertified)	3	5%	0%		•		
	High Environmental Value (certified, France only)	9	15%	100%		•		•
	Other environmental certification	2	3%	0%			•	
	French eco-scheme (practices pathway)	6	10%	100%		•		
<i>Individual parcel-based Agri-environmental Practices not covered above and not required by regulation or conditionality:</i>								
Soil & Crop Management	No use of (phyto-)sanitary measures	12	19%	50%		•		
	Reduced/managed use of (phyto-) sanitary measures	17	27%	33%			•	
	No use of synthetic fertilizers	13	21%	46%		•		
	Reduced/managed use of synthetic fertilizers	15	24%	53%		•	•	
	No tilling	4	6%	25%	•			
Landscape & Habitat Management	Less frequent mowing of grassland	5	8%	0%	•	•		
	Establishment of trees and hedges	5	8%	20%	•			
	Maintenance of (scattered fruit) trees	23	37%	30%		•		
	Landscape conservation	14	23%	57%		•		
Biodiversity Conservation	Hydrological landscape elements	3	5%	33%			•	
	Conservation of plant biodiversity	14	23%	79%		•	•	
	Conservation of animal biodiversity	9	15%	56%		•		
Animals	High Nature Value farming	5	8%	80%		•		
Animals	Animal welfare measures	10	16%	55%		•		
Other	Other	7	11%	0%		•		

Source: Authors' own development.

4.2 Additionality and permanence of AES-supported practices

A key question for CAP effectiveness concerns the extent to which financial incentives trigger additional environmental practices *versus* rewarding practices, which would have been implemented anyway. Table 5 presents farmers' self-reported assessments of additionality and permanence (see Supplementary Material for a cross-border breakdown).

Table 5: Subjective assessment by farms (N=62) of the additionality and permanence of financially supported agri-environmental farming systems and individual practices implemented for 2024 in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France)

	n (farms)	%
ADDITIONALITY		
Agri-environmental farming systems	17	
Low (would certify/participate anyway)	11	65
Partial (would implement some)	n/a	
High (would not without support)	6	35
Individual agri-environmental practices	30	
Low (would implement all anyway)	13	43
Partial (would implement some)	12	40
High (would not implement any without support)	5	17
PERMANENCE		
Agri-environmental farming systems	15	
Permanent integration	11	73
Would stop immediately	0	0
Would continue <2 years	3	20
Not sure	1	7
Individual agri-environmental practices	18	
Permanent integration	14	78
Would stop immediately	4	22
Would continue <2 years	0	0
Not sure	0	0

Note: Additionality and permanence assessments cover two ordinal scale questions: whether farmers would implement agri-environmental activities without support and what they would do with the agri-environmental activity if the contract ended today.

Source: Authors' own development.

Additionality

Farmers' responses indicate considerable deadweight effects across both individual agri-environmental measures and agri-environmental farming systems. Most respondents stated that they would have implemented the respective measures or farm systems even without financial support. High financial additionality was reported for only a small number of measures.

While the sample size does not allow us to draw robust conclusions at the level of individual AES-supported practice categories, indicative patterns emerge. Practices with high reported additionality tended to be labor-intensive, landscape-oriented practices such as mowing steep slopes with cutter bars, artisan viticulture, or extensive management of protected areas (Natura 2000, biotopes). By contrast, measures and certifications with independent commercial or agronomic rationale, notably organic and HVE certification, showed low subsidy dependence. The factors shaping these patterns are examined in greater detail in section 4.3. For French viticulturists in particular, this commercial rationale was often externally enforced: membership in wine cooperatives was conditional on HVE certification, with non-certifying members penalized through substantial price discounts ("*[without HVE] they paid 30% less for the grapes [...] it is the large retailers who demand it*", FR-52). Such buyer-imposed requirements both introduce and sustain certification independently of CAP support, which helps explain the low additionality and high permanence observed for these whole-farm approaches: the practice persists because the market, not the subsidy, requires it. However, larger-scale studies would be necessary to confirm the generalizability of these observations.

Permanence

The picture for permanence is distinctly polarized. Among farmers who responded to the permanence items, 73–78% stated they would permanently integrate their agri-environmental practices into their

farming system regardless of future payments. Another 20–22% stated they would stop immediately or continue for less than two years only. No respondent selected the intermediate continuation options (2–5 years, >5 years), suggesting that farmers hold clear expectations about whether a practice will outlast its financial support. This pattern is consistent with the interpretation that practices are either already embedded in farm identity and operations or perceived as externally imposed obligations that would not survive the removal of compensation.

The low level of additionality observed in the payments, coupled with the high permanence of existing measures, suggests that the farmers interviewed perceive the incentives more as recognition of investments already made, with positive stabilization effects, than as a means of encouraging farmers to adopt new measures and change their behavior. Subsidies compensate for practices that are already embedded in farm management rather than triggering new ones. The exception is the labor-intensive, landscape-oriented measures for which farmers reported high financial additionality. These are the same practices farmers said they would stop once payments ended. Although the results point to meaningful variation between AES-supported practice categories in this regard, the sample size precludes firm generalizations.

4.3 Factors shaping adoption

Based on 792 coded statements, Table 6 and Table 7 present the distribution of adoption factors across the four COM-C dimensions and their constituent primary code clusters. The analysis distinguishes between cross-cutting factors, that is, conditions influencing overall AES participation (e.g., high transaction costs associated with CAP application procedures), and factors shaping the adoption of specific agri-environmental practices (e.g., reduced input costs from lower agrochemical use).

Table 6: Distribution of coded statements on the factors influencing the adoption of agri-environmental farming systems and individual practices by 62 farmers in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France) for 2024 across COM-C dimension and factor type

	Cross-cutting factors (n=394)				Farm system and practice-specific factors (n=398)			
	n	%	(+)	(-)	n	%	(+)	(-)
Motivation	36	9.1%	26	10	200	50.3%	110	89
Capability	39	9.9%	1	38	16	4.0%	0	16
Opportunity	217	55.1%	50	162	138	34.7%	28	108
Context	102	25.9%	3	99	44	11.1%	1	43
Total	394	100%	80	309	398	100%	139	256

Notes: (+) = drivers/enabling factors; (-) = barriers/constraining factors.

In some cells (+) + (-) ≠ n due to statements coded as neutral (0) or mixed valence.

Source: Authors' own development.

Table 7: Distribution of coded statements on the factors influencing the adoption of agri-environmental farming systems and individual practices by 62 farmers in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France) for 2024 across COM-C dimension and code cluster

Dimension	Code cluster	<i>n</i> statements	%	(+)	(-)
Motivation	Operational impacts	80	10.1	43	36
	Economic & Financial	79	10	33	46
	Values & Identity	59	7.4	44	15
	Environmental & Health	18	2.3	16	2
	<i>Motivation subtotal</i>	<i>236</i>	<i>29.8</i>	<i>136</i>	<i>99</i>
Capability	Resources	40	5.1	1	39
	Saturation	12	1.5	0	12
	Knowledge	3	0.4	0	3
	<i>Capability subtotal</i>	<i>55</i>	<i>6.9</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>54</i>
Opportunity	Scheme Design & Menu	121	15.3	18	101
	Administrative & Transaction Burden	80	10.1	10	68
	Payment Adequacy	75	9.5	38	37
	Monitoring, Verification & Compliance	43	5.4	1	42
	Implementation Support	14	1.8	6	6
	Biophysical & Practice Feasibility	12	1.5	0	12
	Social Environment	10	1.3	5	5
	<i>Opportunity subtotal</i>	<i>355</i>	<i>44.8</i>	<i>78</i>	<i>271</i>
Context	Market & Economic System	55	6.9	1	54
	Policy & Governance	49	6.2	1	48
	Social & Cultural	23	2.9	0	23
	Infrastructure & Services	15	1.9	1	14
	Environmental Context	4	0.5	1	3
	<i>Context subtotal</i>	<i>146</i>	<i>18.4</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>142</i>
Total		792	100	219	565

Note: Rows where (+) and (-) do not sum to *n* contain neutral-coded statements

Source: Authors' own development.

4.3.1 Motivation

Motivation references account for 236 coded statements across 62 interviewed farmers, making this the second-largest dimension and the only one in which positive references outweigh negative ones (136 vs. 99). The cross-border distribution was nearly balanced (111 statements from German and 125 from French respondents). The dimension is strongly practice-relevant: 200 of the 236 references (85%) relate to specific incentivized practices rather than to general AES participation, and at the practice level Motivation is by far the dominant dimension (50.3% of practice-related references, see Table 6). This indicates that farmers hold differentiated and often well-articulated views on the merits of individual practices, even where they criticize the surrounding AES architecture. The valence patterns differ markedly across clusters, as shown in Table 7.

Values and identity were the most positively skewed cluster (44 positive, 15 negative), with farmers frequently framing adoption as an expression of personal conviction: "*It must be consistent with one's own convictions*" (FR-05). For some, the practice long predates any incentive: "*I have always farmed organically, even before it existed as a label*" (DE-18). This pattern suggests that for a substantial subgroup, agri-environmental practice is experienced as identified or intrinsic motivation in the Self-Determination Theory sense, not as compliance with external incentives but as an enactment of who the farmer considers themselves to be. Economic and financial factors, by contrast, showed the most negative valence (33 positive, 46 negative), with part-time and smaller farms particularly affected: "*Bio is bad for part-timers: work, time, weeds, and area yield all suffer*" (DE-33). The tension between these two clusters, namely strong value-based motivation coexisting with economic barriers, is a defining feature of the Motivation dimension and underscores why payment design alone cannot fully explain adoption behavior.

Operational impacts, the largest cluster within Motivation (80 statements), were also the most evenly balanced in valence (43 positive, 36 negative), reflecting a pragmatic appraisal of how each practice fits farm operations. Positive judgements centered on private operational co-benefits such as reduced labor and input use, improved soil life, or drought resilience ("*less mowing means less soil compaction, less diesel, and less time; only a small tractor is needed*", DE-36; and "*if the measure works technically and is of benefit to the soil, enrolment happens*", DE-07); these self-justifying benefits help explain why such practices are maintained independently of payment, reinforcing the low additionality reported in section 4.2.

Negative judgements, by contrast, concentrated on agroforestry, where trees were repeatedly seen as obstructing machinery and competing with crops, which is consistent with its more limited uptake. A distinct class of negative operational appraisals concerned not the practice itself but its embedded restriction: prohibitions on fertilization in Natura 2000 areas were reported to encourage moss encroachment that progressively rendered steep slopes slippery for tractors, illustrating how a measure designed for one environmental objective can compromise farm operability and, with it, the long-run permanence of the very land use it seeks to protect.

An in-depth look at the farmers' motivations

The standardized analysis of the 20 Self-Determination Theory items measuring farmer motivation types and need-based dimensions confirmed that farmers' engagement into agri-environmental practices was predominantly driven by Identified and Intrinsic Motivation (Figure 3a), grounded in a strong personal commitment to environmental stewardship. Introjected Motivation (moral responsibility) also played a role, whereas External Motivation scored notably lower, and Amotivation was minimal.

Figure 3: Motivations for adoption of agri-environmental farming systems and individual practices and basic psychological needs satisfaction of farmers (N=62) in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France)

Source: Authors' own development based on items developed by Gagné (2003), Mayer & Frantz (2004), Pelletier et al. (1998) and Ryan & Deci (2000).

Among the three basic psychological needs (Figure 3b), Relatedness was most strongly satisfied (both social, $M=3.26$, and nature-related, $M=3.19$), followed by Competence ($M=3.06$), while Autonomy showed the lowest satisfaction score of the three dimensions ($M=2.89$).

Cross-border comparisons reveal broadly similar motivational profiles overall, with French farmers reporting marginally higher autonomous motivation across the Intrinsic-Integrated-Identified spectrum. The two most pronounced cross-border differences sit at the controlled-to-amotivated end of the continuum: French farmers report substantially higher Introjected motivation ($M = 3.06$ vs. 2.48 in Germany) and higher Amotivation ($M = 2.34$ vs. 1.76), while German farmers report marginally higher satisfaction of basic psychological needs, particularly for social relatedness (see Supplementary Material).

Structural associations

The cross-tabulation of farm characteristics with adopted practice categories, quantified using the Phi coefficient (Figure 4), reveals systematic patterns that triangulate the qualitative COM-C findings reported above.

Figure 4: Structural associations between binary characteristics of farms ($N=62$) and of adopted agri-environmental farming systems and individual practices in Landkreis Ortenau (Germany) and Arrondissement of Molsheim (France) for 2024

Notes: ↔ denotes association (not causality). ϕ measures the strength of association between two binary variables on a scale from -1 to $+1$. Medium ($\phi=0.3$) and large ($\phi=0.5$) thresholds based on (Cohen, 2013). Only associations with $n \geq 5$ and $\phi \geq 0.3$ are shown.

Source: Authors' own development.

Grassland and mountain farms show the strongest structural associations with input-reduction practices, consistent with management embedded in operational routine rather than adopted in response to policy incentives. Organic certification aligns structurally with perennial farms, where viticultural premium markets support its viability, while HVE aligns with lowland farms, suggesting that certification-based and practice-based instruments effectively target different structural segments. Most consequentially, the negative associations in the dataset reveal a compensation paradox. Farms with AES-supported practices are significantly less likely to maintain scattered fruit trees ($\phi = -0.73$), to engage in other voluntary practices outside the formal scheme catalogue ($\phi = -0.58$), to reduce phytosanitary product use ($\phi = -0.56$), to mow grassland less frequently ($\phi = -0.48$), or to abandon synthetic fertilizers ($\phi = -0.31$), indicating that the most additional environmental practices in the sample are driven predominantly by non-compensated, voluntarily adopting farms. This intersects directly with the additionality findings of section 4.2 and the motivational analysis above, and is taken up in the Discussion.

4.3.2 Capability

Capability constraints relating to the internal resources, knowledge, and capacity of the farmer-farm-unit were cited in 55 coded references across 32 of the 62 interviewed farmers, making this the most uniformly negative dimension in the sample, with 54 of 55 statements framing Capability as a barrier. The distribution was broadly comparable across the border (28 statements from German and 27 from French respondents), though the specific constraints differed in emphasis: German farmers more frequently cited labor shortages on part-time mountain farms, while French farmers more often raised land-related structural constraints including parcel fragmentation. The dimension is dominated by Resources (40 statements, 73%), followed by Saturation (22%) and Knowledge (5%).

Resources were dominated by labor constraints, with family farms and part-time operations reporting that workforce limitations directly restrict the range of adoptable practices: *"Hiring is too expensive [...] the CAP must be linked to the number of people working on the farm, not the number of hectares"* (FR-39). On the French side, land-structural constraints were more prominent, with parcel fragmentation directly limiting practice feasibility: *"Small, scattered parcels do not allow natural manure to be spread when the plots lie too far apart"* (FR-09). Saturation (12 statements) captured a distinct constraint not identified in any of the eight reviews synthesized in Table 1 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** It was particularly prevalent in perennial and permanent grassland. In these systems, farmers judged that they had already enrolled all compatible land and exhausted the available measure catalogue. As one respondent put it, "I'm doing the maximum, I cannot do any more than that" (FR-02).

4.3.3 Opportunity

Opportunity factors capturing all conditions external to the farmer-farm-unit that enable or constrain adoption account for the largest share of coded references (355 statements, 45% of all references), and represent the most substantial source of barriers (270 vs. 78). German farmers raised disproportionately more Opportunity concerns than French farmers (215 vs. 140 statements), reflecting greater frustration with the German subsidy framework. Notably, AES participation itself differs markedly across the border: 74% of German respondents participated in at least one AECM (primarily FAKT II), whereas only 48% of French respondents participated in the eco-scheme, with very limited AECM uptake. This low French uptake is not an artefact of the sample: in unpublished regional administrative data for the 2024 campaign, the two Alsatian *départements*, Bas-Rhin (which contains the Molsheim study area) and Haut-Rhin, recorded among the lowest system-level AECM uptake of the ten *départements* in the Grand Est region (CRAEC Grand Est, 2025). This pattern is discussed further in the Discussion. Following our framework, Opportunity is structured into three sub-

dimensions: policy-created conditions (clusters covering AES design, administrative burden, payments, monitoring, and implementation support, together 333 statements, 94% of the dimension); the immediate social environment (10 statements); and the universal biophysical and structural feasibility of practices themselves (12 statements).

AES design and menu factors formed the largest Opportunity cluster (121 statements, 34%), dominated by complaints about rigidity: fixed commitment periods, prescribed timing windows, and combinability rules. The five-year commitment drew the most frequent objection: *"The five-year commitment is not good, because there is no guarantee it works; it is an experiment. One year would be better, and if it works the farmer will continue anyway"* (DE-07). Administrative and transaction burden (80 statements, 23%) was the single most frequently cited barrier across the entire study. Several French farmers described the CAP and particularly the eco-scheme as an *"usine à gaz"*, a French idiom for excessively convoluted processes (FR-09, FR-10, FR-52, FR-55). Implementation support (14 statements, 4%) was small and balanced in valence. Subsidized advisory exists on both sides, through accredited organizations in Baden-Württemberg and chambers of agriculture in Alsace. French farmers valued the chamber's application help but called it fee-based and reactive (FR-03, FR-09), while German farmers wanted the lower agricultural authorities to advise rather than only control (DE-04). The substantive difference is structural. Formal advisory accompaniment is embedded in the French area-based AECM through the operator (*structure animatrice*), but not in FAKT II or the eco-scheme.

4.3.4 Context

Context factors operate at the systems level, capturing market conditions, international competition, regulatory coherence, societal appreciation, infrastructure, and environmental conditions that lie beyond the direct control of AES designers. With 146 coded statements (18% of total), Context is the third-largest dimension, and 142 of these (97%) were coded as barriers, the highest barrier-to-driver ratio of any dimension. German farmers raised notably more Context concerns than their French counterparts (88 vs. 55 statements), with the emphasis differing across themes: German farmers focused more on trade exposure and retail-chain power asymmetries, while French farmers raised concerns about societal appreciation and declining rural infrastructure more frequently. This concentration is consequential. Context factors shape the structural environment in which agri-environmental practices operate and require interventions that go beyond agri-environmental policy itself, are slower-moving, and often demand cross-sectoral coordination.

Market and economic system factors (55 statements, 38%) dominate the dimension. Farmers consistently framed their agri-environmental engagement as inseparable from economic survival: *"Most people here only survive on the CAP. That's the big problem; we don't want money from the government, we want a fair price for our products"* (FR-01). International trade exposure emerged as a recurrent concern, with farmers drawing direct connections between global market dynamics and their willingness to invest in environmental practice: *"Mercosur triggers a race to the bottom in terms of agri-environmental practices"* (DE-07). Beyond market structures, farmers pointed to an erosion of societal appreciation for their stewardship: *"There is no public appreciation of the Black Forest landscape and what the farmer does to maintain it; people enjoy the scenery on holiday but never ask where it comes from"* (DE-08). These statements illustrate why the analytical separation of Context from Opportunity matters. No redesign of eco-scheme payment rates or AECM contract terms can address the structural conditions that farmers describe here. These statements constitute the strongest empirical justification for the COM-C extension proposed in this paper.

5 DISCUSSION

Five key findings emerge from the results. First, the 62 farms implement a wide range of agri-environmental systems and practices, 186 in total, delivered through two major channels. These are whole-farm approaches and individual parcel-based practices. A substantial share is carried out voluntarily, without payment. Second, strong motivation met constrained conditions for action. Farmers' motivation was rooted in values, identity, and environmental or health concerns. Accordingly, 'Motivation' was the only area in our four-dimensional framework where drivers outweighed barriers. Yet farmers also voiced many reservations within this area, mainly about profitability and the practicalities of implementation. Third, French and German farmers shared similar motivational profiles and differed mainly in what they criticized. German farmers focused on the design of individual measures, French farmers on the whole-farm certification architecture. This contrast reflects two national policy designs, not different biophysical or market conditions. Fourth, AES functioned more as recognition of existing effort than as a catalyst for change. Low additionality coincided with high permanence of already-adopted AES-supported practices. The few high-additionality measures were exactly those that farmers said they would abandon once payments ended. Fifth, the wider economic and societal context emerged as an almost uniformly negative constraint. It includes trade exposure, retailer market power, policy incoherence, and low public recognition. These conditions sit beyond the reach of agri-environmental policy itself.

Strong motivation, voice, and partial exit

In our sample, AES incentives mostly supported practices that were already well aligned with farmers' intrinsic motivations. Farmers accordingly experienced these payments as a reward for environmental stewardship rather than as a trigger for change. In parallel, respondents reported implementing a substantial share of environmental practices voluntarily, outside any scheme. This reading aligns with review evidence that intrinsic values and environmental concern drive adoption at least as much as economic incentives (Dessart et al., 2019; Klebl et al., 2024), and that administrative burden and inflexible rules act as major barriers to adoption (Bartkowski et al., 2023). It also fits with the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), in which attitudes and self-identity shape behavior, and with Self-Determination Theory, in which autonomous motivation sustains action without external control (Pelletier et al., 1998). It also explains how farmers handled the constrained conditions for action, namely through voice and partial exit (Hirschman, 1970). They criticized administrative requirements, rigid contracts, and monitoring friction while remaining enrolled. In parallel, respondents reported implementing a substantial share of environmental practices voluntarily, outside any scheme (see Section 4.1). The handling is low-cost because, as respondents repeatedly suggested, agri-environmental support accounts for only a marginal share of their farm income.⁷ Partial exit also helps explain why we found no indications of motivational crowding out, contrary to a recurring concern in the literature (Akers & Yasué, 2019; Ezzine-de-Blas et al., 2019; Lokhorst et al., 2011; Rode et al., 2015). Crowding out requires that payments are experienced as controlling. Where farmers enrolled, the payment instead rewarded what they were already doing, so it worked as recognition rather than control. The strength of intrinsic motivation in our sample points the same way. Had the payments crowded it out, it would not have remained the strongest dimension in our framework (see Figure 3). This recognition function carries over into the additionality findings discussed below.

We argue that German AES may accommodate this recognition function more readily than the French. Contracting existing individual parcel-based practices rewards and stabilizes the status quo, implicitly recognizing farmers as "responsible" food producers, whereas French AES target whole-farm

⁷ At EU level, direct payments represented on average about 23% of agricultural factor income in 2018 to 2022, and total subsidies about 33% (European Commission, 2024). These figures cover all direct payments, dominated by basic income support. Agri-environmental support is only a fraction of this total.

transformation with higher ambition. Yet the share of supported practices that were financially additional was similarly low on both sides. Because our sample principally captures the maintenance stage of these systems, it cannot speak to the additionality of earlier conversion decisions, such as the wave of organic conversion in France.

Beyond payment levels: advisory capacity and contract design

The transaction costs of AES have long been recognized as a central barrier to participation (Bartkowski et al., 2023; Espinosa Diaz et al., 2023; Falconer, 2000). Our findings confirm this and add a comparative dimension. French farmers described locally accessible help from the agricultural chamber at the contracting stage, though some found it fee-based and reactive rather than proactive (FR-03, FR-09). German farmers instead criticized the shift of the lower agricultural authorities away from advice toward administration and control (DE-04). The offices still help with the annual FIONA declaration, but respondents saw this as narrower than the chamber's technical support. This reflects the restructuring of advisory provision in Baden-Württemberg, where specialized advice was transferred to accredited private organizations from 2015 (MLR, 2026; Birke et al., 2022).

This contrast suggests that dedicated and locally accessible advisory structures underpin behavioral change (Mills et al., 2017; Espinosa-Goded et al., 2010). Advice is among the few determinants that syntheses find robustly and positively associated with uptake (Schaub et al., 2023; Canessa et al., 2024). If advisory capacity weighs as much as our cases suggest, payment levels may matter less than is sometimes assumed. A regional administrative survey for the previous French CAP period points the same way. AECM beneficiaries in the Grand Est ranked payment delays as the leading difficulty (36% of 1,328 respondents), ahead of understanding the cahier des charges (15%) and technical implementation (12%), and over 70% reported no advisory follow-up after engagement (DRAAF Grand Est & Région Grand Est, 2020).

That follow-up gap frames the earlier period rather than our own findings, and it has an architectural cause specific to the French AECM. AECMs are implemented in response to environmental challenges but only where a project operator (*structure animatrice*) comes forward, typically a chamber, local authority, or nature park. They coordinate the project and support participating farmers technically (DRAAF Grand Est, 2022). This dependency is reciprocal. Where no operator comes forward, no AECM is offered. Molsheim in 2024 is a case in point, with only very specific, non-surface-based AECMs on offer, such as those dedicated to beekeeping and the protection of the European hamster's habitat (CRAEC Grand Est, 2025). Our results reflect this availability gap, not a thinning of advice after contracting. The German FAKT II model enrolls farmers directly, without this territorial gateway, yielding more uniform coverage but no embedded operator. Subsidized advisory still exists in Baden-Württemberg on a voluntary basis, through accredited organizations. What neither model embeds in the scheme itself is continuous advisory accompaniment beyond the application stage.

Without that continuity, the underlying constraint remains. It is administrative burden weighed against an already strong motivation. This maps onto perceived behavioral control in the Theory of Planned Behavior, and onto the non-monetary contract attributes that Random Utility Theory places alongside or above payment, such as complexity, flexibility, and transaction costs (Ruto & Garrod, 2009). The two traditions are often read as competing, one psychological and one economic, but here they describe the same constraint from two angles, which is why recent work treats them as complementary rather than rival (Canessa et al., 2024). Self-Determination Theory completes the picture, distinguishing the quality of motivation from its level in a way neither framework captures.

What drives additionality?

The low additionality we observe corroborates the difference-in-differences estimates of Chabé-Ferret & Subervie (2013), who found substantial deadweight for several French agri-environmental measures. Review evidence likewise flags deadweight as a recurrent concern in scheme design (Schaub et al., 2023). It is also consistent with ex-post evaluations concluding that CAP biodiversity spending has not halted the decline of farmland biodiversity, which points to limited ecological additionality at the program level (Alliance Environnement, 2019; European Court of Auditors, 2020). In our study, the highest financial additionality is found in labor intensive practices that maintain High Nature Value landscapes (Baldock et al., 1994). These require real labor cost and deliver benefits to tourism and biodiversity rather than to production and carbon sequestration through more forests. They are also the measures farmers said they would discontinue once payments ended. This inverse relationship identifies the practices where higher payments would induce behavior that farmers would not otherwise undertake, rather than reward existing effort. It reflects the heterogeneity in agricultural income forgone that underlies incentive compatibility in stewardship schemes (Fraser, 2009). Additionality is low for organic and HVE certification, where market premiums, cooperative policies and established management already sustain the behavior, so that agri-environmental support functions as recognition rather than as compensation for change.

A structural association in our sample points the same way. Farms with AES-supported practices were less likely to also carry the most additional voluntary practices, which were concentrated instead among non-participating farmers. A matched comparison of Bavarian dairy farms points the same way. It found no significant difference in environmental performance between participating and non-participating farms (Ait Sidhoum et al., 2023). This low additionality among participants matches the selection documented in the wider literature, where scheme uptake concentrates among farmers whose practices already meet the requirements (Bartkowski et al., 2023; Kleijn & Sutherland, 2003). Selection thus limits financial additionality, because participants already aligned with AES requirements leave little new behavior to generate. Evidence from the review literature supports this interpretation. AES uptake is shaped by farm and farmer attributes, such as lower dependence on farm income and the presence of a successor, attributes that shape selection into the schemes (Lastra-Bravo et al., 2015). The regional survey noted earlier provides convergent evidence. 36% of respondents would have maintained the same practices without an AECM, a deadweight response found across groups but concentrated among grassland farmers, the only sub-group in which a majority said practices would have continued without payment (DRAAF Grand Est & Région Grand Est, 2020). This suggests that payment plays a limited inducement role for grassland management already sustained through other channels.

Recognition payments for already-aligned practices should carry minimal documentation, simple eligibility, short-term commitments, and proportionate monitoring, treating intrinsic motivation as an asset to preserve rather than a behavior to engineer through conditionality. The administrative architecture farmers most resist (five-year lock-ins, prescriptive AECM specifications, layered monitoring) should be concentrated on the smaller subset of measures where behavior change is genuinely additional, so that the friction farmers tolerate is the friction that produces environmental gain. This differentiation aligns incentive architecture with environmental objectives, a design principle central to both governance and cost-effectiveness accounts of effective AES (Podruzsik & Fertő, 2024; OECD, 2022). The same logic applies one level higher. Whole-farm pathways (eco-scheme, HVE, organic farming) ask for change across the whole farm at once (scaling up), while individual measures spread enrollment across many farms (scaling out). Neither route was clearly more additional in our sample. In both, additionality stayed low because payments mostly *maintained* existing systems rather than establishing new ones. The routes differ in how participation is organized, not in how much additional change they deliver, and neither yet differentiates administrative weight by what the measure requires.

The value of “Context” and porous boundaries

Treating Context as a fourth dimension, alongside Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation, was the most useful step in our analysis. Behavioral models of adoption center the individual, and the wider economic and institutional setting is usually left as residual. Thompson et al. (2024) show how seldom such conditions enter adoption studies, and among the reviews in our synthesis only Klebl et al. (2024) and Lastra-Bravo et al. (2015) build them in. The value of the fourth dimension was clearest in the cross-border comparison. Motivation was largely shared across the two regions, while the binding constraints were context-specific. This is the same split that Mozzato et al. (2018) report, with structural and socioeconomic effects varying geographically and motivational factors holding more consistently. Without Context, we would have read the absence of adoption as an individual shortcoming, when the constraints lay in the wider setting. The dimension also revealed leverage points in trade, competition, and rural development that lie outside agricultural policy.

The boundaries between the four dimensions proved porous, and that porosity was itself informative. Practice compatibility, usually treated as a structural farm condition, was raised by interviewees as a reason to act or to refrain, a motivational appraisal rather than a feasibility constraint. Financial considerations split across two layers, judgments of the wider farm economy and judgments of the adequacy of a specific payment. One recurring constraint fit no category at all. Some farmers perceived that they had exhausted the available AES-supported practices. This saturation matters for additionality, because higher payments cannot unlock further uptake where it applies. Saturation maps onto the feasibility side of the desirability-feasibility distinction drawn in the PES literature (Mayr et al., 2025).

Our findings speak to the broader notion of effectiveness set out at the start, where additionality and permanence sit alongside cost-effectiveness, timing, and scale (Mayr et al., 2025). Read together, they point to a trade-off between the two conditions. Autonomously motivated participation tends toward low additionality but high permanence, since the practice persists without continued payment. Externally regulated participation tends toward the reverse, with change that can lapse once the contract ends. A uniform payment cannot serve both cases, because paying to induce change wastes resources on farmers who would act anyway, while paying to recognize existing practice does little to move the reluctant. This points toward differentiated design rather than a single uniform instrument, though its reach is bounded by the wider context that ran through our analysis.

6 CONCLUSION

This study examined how 62 farmers in the German and French parts of the Upper Rhine region adopt agri-environmental practices and engage with AES under contrasting national policy architectures. For most respondents, agri-environmental support recognizes and stabilizes environmental management already embedded in the farm rather than triggering new behavior.

What differs between France and Germany is less farmer motivation, comparable on both sides, than the architecture through which it meets policy. The French approach of supporting whole-farm agri-environmental transformations (eco-scheme practices pathway, HVE, organic farming) bundles support into a single farm-wide commitment, while the German individual-measure approach reaches a broader population but leaves advisory support optional rather than embedded in the scheme. Neither system yet calibrates its administrative demands to whether a measure recognizes existing practice or aims to induce new behavior.

Some of the most consequential constraints on agri-environmental engagement, however, lie beyond agri-environmental policy. Respondents repeatedly emphasized that AES-supported practices operate at the level of symptoms, while the binding constraints lie further upstream. They pointed to three in particular. The first is the pricing power of retail chains. The second is exposure to trade arrangements that do not enforce equivalent environmental standards, most prominently the EU-Mercosur agreement, which respondents named as a race-to-the-bottom risk. The third is the gap between what society expects of farmers and the prices it is willing to pay for their products. The recurrent demand among our respondents for fair product prices rather than subsidies reflects not a rejection of environmental ambition but the recognition that green farming presupposes a viable farming economy. Closing that gap calls for levers that lie outside the CAP toolbox itself, such as shortened supply chains and local marketing, the rebalancing of retail concentration, trade-policy coherence with domestic environmental standards, and a broader public recognition of the landscape and ecosystem services that farming sustains. Without progress on these conditions, even well-designed agri-environmental instruments cannot deliver against expectations that farmers cannot afford to meet.

Scaling agri-environmental practice in the EU therefore has two distinct margins. Scaling out, the breadth of enrollment, is already wide, but it adds little where it recruits existing practice. Scaling up, the additional environmental benefit per farm, is where the design effort belongs. As in the agroforestry case (Mayr et al., 2025), enrollment is a necessary but not sufficient condition for environmental gain. The task is therefore less to pay *more* than to pay *better*. This means distinguishing measures that genuinely induce behavior change from those that recognize existing practice. It also means preserving intrinsic motivation through shorter commitments, simpler rules, and stronger advisory support. Finally, it means aligning agri-environmental policy with the trade, market, and societal conditions on which green farming livelihoods depend.

Our results suggest four lines of further research. First, our farmers reported administrative and advisory burden as a barrier. Transaction costs of AES have been measured, but rarely across measures or tied to behavioral barriers. Future work could do both. Second, permanence is best observed after a contract ends, through revisit designs, not single visits. Existing evidence rests on stated intentions, so direct observation would add more. Third, additionality is usually estimated with difference-in-differences, which needs panel or administrative data. Where these are unavailable, our triangulated design offers a complement. Pre-enrollment motivational profiles could build matched comparison groups, addressing the self-selection of pre-compliant farmers that weakens additionality. Fourth, whether our recognition-versus-incentive pattern generalizes beyond public AES remains open. Voluntary carbon market schemes offer a structurally different test case, where additionality testing is a certification requirement.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

S.M.: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **B.P.:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review and editing. **E.C.:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review and editing.

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Data availability

The raw interview transcripts that support the findings of this study are not publicly available due to privacy restrictions and the conditions of informed consent. Given the localized nature of agricultural communities, sharing full transcripts could compromise the anonymity of the participating farmers. The codebook used for the analysis is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the first author used a large language model (Claude Opus 4, Anthropic) in order to assist with aspects of manuscript preparation, specifically for linguistic refinement and the structuring of arguments. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the work.

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